

Towards Design Marketplace Web-Based GIS for Crowdsourced Data Spatial Using API Method

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Abstract — MAPI is a geographic information system that applies the concept of crowdsourced marketplace geographic information data which is expected to be one of the facilitators in facilitating geographic data makers especially with KML format in sharing geographic information data owned, in addition to the form of GeoJSON API format. so that users can be facilitated in integrating or utilizing digital spatial data to develop systems or applications based on mobile or web. Utilization of RabbitMQ's message queue method to help the system to serve a lot of requests so it doesn't burden the hardware used in the MAPI system

Keywords — Geographic Information System, Crowdsourced Data Spatial, Data Spatial Integration, API, Message Queue

I INTRODUCTION

Geographical Information System is one of the effects of the influence of the rapid development of information technology on the geospatial field. The rapid addition of very large information data at each point of the earth's coordinates due to the development of geospatial data recording technology, both using satellite media, mobile applications, web-based applications and much more.

In its own use, geographic information systems are widely used as one of the supporting data for policy making in a regional planning, spatial planning. Supporting data of the geographical information system itself can be either spatial or non-spatial data. Spatial data itself is data that describes the surface of the earth represented in raster maps in the form of graphs, maps, images or vector maps in the form of dots, lines and polygons.

But to produce a geographic information system that can help make planning requires the support of accurate and up-to-date thematic sources of data and information that describe the condition of an area that can be easily understood. But unfortunately to realize a good geographic information system there are problems - such as lack of or even unavailability of digital geographic data and to obtain data or information on

digital thematic maps that are good requires a long time and relatively expensive costs.

Figure 1 Map's Type and Layer

II BACKGROUND

Seeing and mapping the data needed to support information systems that can be one of the supporting materials for making plans, this research was conducted to develop a system called MAPI, which is expected by MAPI as a geospatial data service provider that can facilitate geographic data makers, especially for Digital vector maps in publishing data created and collaborating with users who need vector data to support the development of applications or systems that will be developed.

Figure 2 Utilization of GIS for the development of Volunteered Geographic Information applications

MAPI is an application product intended to be a web-based geographic data market developed to accommodate the needs of digital geographic data users and the desire to share or collaborate digital geographic data for digital geographic data makers. Therefore, the design of the MAPI system must cover aspects of the needs of geographic data users and digital geographic data makers that make the user experience feel comfortable and easy to use the MAPI system. The author uses the rapid prototyping method, the author chooses the rapid prototyping method in the development of the MAPI system with the aim of being able to do market matching so that the writer can get feedback, whether the system has met the needs of system users.

Figure 3 Flow Rapid Prototyping Method

Input data sources that are the basis of processing as information in the form of current digital vector map data with the Key Markup Language (KML) format. The reason KML is used as a data source is tested in the development of the full MAPI system, because KML is an XML language that is focused on the need to visualize digital geographic data, both in the form of annotations, coordinates and images. Referring to KML or now OpenGIS® KML Encoding Standard (OGC KML), originally developed by Google and submitted to the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) to evolve in the OGC consensus process with the aim of being standardized in OGC implementation for GIS development or VGI applications or systems both 2D and 3D maps.

While for the output of the data source processing in the form of GeoJSON which already has international standards, so that it can be used and reused from the output to develop a system or application by utilizing the output of the MAPI system. GeoJSON is not a new concept, GeoJSON is a development of the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) structure format with standard [RFC7159] specifically for handling types of geometry data that can accommodate the use of geographic data for web-based applications, mobile devices or client-server-based systems.

The selection of application concepts as a means of marketplace crowdsource geographic data is because the author sees unlimited possibilities in the use of digital geographic data in technology development, so the authors choose the use of geographic data integration using existing and widely used methods, namely application programming interface (API) in GeoJSON format. In this study, the author also uses RabbitMQ

as a message broker that manages the queue of data processing requests from client to server.

Figure 4 Integration Data Map Layer

III ANALYSIS AND SYSTEM DESIGN

Minimum environmental requirements for the devices that I use in developing the MAPI system are as follows:

- 1 unit PC server with specification:
 - 1) CPU : Proesor Intel® Xeon® E3-1220 v3, cache 8M, 3,10 GHz
 - 2) Memory : 16Gb
 - 3) Motherboard : Intel® Server Board S1200V3RPL
- Environment software used to support system development, namely :
 - 1) Windows Server 2012 R2
 - 2) Laravel 5.6
 - 3) MySQL 5.5
 - 4) IIS 8
 - 5) PHP 7.2.2
- The software used as a testing tool includes
 - 1) Google Earth
 - 2) Cesium
 - 3) GeoJSON.io
 - 4) Unity
 - 5) Leaflet
 - 6) Apache Benchmark
 - 7) Jmeter

The MAPI system design architecture can be seen in the figure below :

Figure 5 Flow System Architecture

The target specification of the feature requirements to be achieved by the author in designing and developing the MAPI system are as follows:

- 1) To store KML files into the system.
- 2) Read the contents of the KML file data and process it into an output in the form of an API with the GeoJSON format structure in accordance with applicable standards.
- 3) Save the contents of the KML file data source into the database.
- 4) Handle many of the GeoJSON API output requests from many clients.

The flow of interaction designed and developed can be seen in the picture "MAPI interaction system".

Figure 6 MAPI interaction system

[8] The flow of interaction contained in the MAPI system design consists of the process of entering or storing data sources in the form of geographic data with KML format by the KML maker into the system, then the user can add or create APIs from the KML file data that has been entered into the system which later The API that was created and published can be used to be part of the development of applications or systems that are made in the form of applications or web-based systems or mobile devices.

IV IMPLEMENTATION

In the process of processing the projection of spatial data in the database into a digital map, the author uses the merkator method as a method of projecting. Merkator projection methods are usually written in formulas:

$$\chi = R\lambda$$

$$y = R \ln \tan \left(\frac{1}{4} \pi + \frac{1}{2} \phi \right)$$

To realize the goal, namely as an application that can accommodate in sharing geographic data, therefore in this study, the authors conducted testing for each phase of the full moon development. In this paper, the authors divide the test into 2 parts, namely standardization testing and stress tests.

Before explaining the series of standardized tests that have been carried out in the full development phase, the purpose of standardization testing is carried out, among others:

- 1) To assess the assessment of data sources that will be used as data sources can accommodate user needs.
- 2) Is the output in the form of an API with GeoJSON format in accordance with standardization so that it can run well.

Figure 7 Test KML - Rendering Polygon 3D using Unity

Figure 8 Test GeoJSON - Standard Mapbox

In conducting standardized testing, testers use a tool that is useful as a measuring tool whether the output produced is in accordance with applicable standards. Tests are carried out using KML format data by displaying the contents of KML data into 2D and 3D digital maps where the results of KML can be run in many test cases such as unity, google earth, cesium, in terms of data content in KML in more detail than OSM and to be developed into an API because the KML structure itself is an XML format commonly used for API creation. Whereas the output in the form of GeoJson is tested by using the API in GeoJson format on the GeoJson.io site and displaying a map using a leaflet which results in the GeoJson format that is output according to the standard, which is marked by running dialat which is the test benchmark.

Another type of testing done by the author in research and development of the MAPI system is a stress test. Just like standardization testing, in the stress test in this study the testers used tools to do the testing including JMeter and Apache Benchmark. The objectives of the testing include:

- 1) Measurement of the maximum number of requests that can be served at one time.
- 2) The level of performance system in handling many requests from users.
- 3) Looking for benchmarks whether the system designed has met the minimum requirements to be released into the production stage or not.

As can be seen in the data request flow diagram image in the initial full development phase, the author has not used the database as a storage medium and data source but uses KML files uploaded as the data source and also the author has not used message queue to set the queue of data requests that enter server.

Figure 9 Request Data Flow Chart

Figure 10 Stress Test Graph

Table 1 Stress Test

Detil	Request				
	50	100	200	400	800
Time taken for test (minutes)	15	27.13	66	130	185
Failed request0	0	0	0	0	142
Total transferred (Mb)	1.74	3.48	6.96	13.92	23
HTML transferred	1.72	3.45	6.9	13.81	22
Request per second (mean)	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.07
Time per request (Second, Mean)	27.98	27.13	20	19.57	13.88

Transfer Rate (Kbps)	1.27	1.31	1.77	1.82	2.12
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As can be seen in the statistical graph and table above, the results of stress test testing using tools with KML 1 bandung data with a file size of 54MB and requests made by sorting parameters, shows that the architecture can serve requests up to 1000 requests not in 1 network is good even though in the case of testing 800 requests failed, the request was 142 requests because the client's internet connection constraints were interrupted for a while. But for performance speed in completing requests is felt to be quite time consuming, it might be because the data retrieval process is done by retrieving data from data sources that form KML files and without indexing so that it takes time to manage data to be output according to demand.

Purnarupa versi beta mengembangkan konsep dari purnarupa versi alpha tetapi masih menggunakan rancang disain arsitektur infrastruktur yang sama dengan purnarupa versi alpha. Pengembangan atau perbaikan yang dilakukan pada purnarupa versi beta sendiri meliputi penambahan message queue dengan perangkat lunak RabbitMQ dan penyimpanan data spasial ke dalam database.

Figure 11 Graph Beta Full Performance Test Results

Table 2 Performance Testing by Using MySQL Databases and RMQ

Detil	Request				
	50	100	200	400	800

Time taken for test (minutes)	2	1.62	3.27	6.59	17.46
Failed request0	0	0	0	0	0
Total transferred (Mb)	1.8	3.6	6.5	12.7	27.1
HTML transferred	1.8	3.6	6.5	12.7	27.1
Request per second (mean)	0.41	1.03	1.03	1.01	0.76
Time per request (Second, Mean)	2.4	0.97	0.96	0.98	1.3
Transfer Rate (Kbps)	15.07	37.93	34.56	33.04	26.55

The results of the beta version of the full development performance test show better results in terms of processing in handling multiple user requests at the same time. We can see from the tables and graphs above, that using a database as a storage medium for KML data and using message queue software to manage the user request service process can speed up the request processing time wherein the alpha version does not use the database and message queue to 1 second service process cannot complete 1 user request but on the full beta version on average for each test case in 1 second can complete 1 request. The service process can still be accelerated because of the function of indexing the data in the database so that if there are data that is often requested by the user, the data search process will be stored in the index function and data search process without having to enter storage.

V CONCLUSION

The results of the research and system development tests that have been carried out, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- Features developed in the system have been running well according to the target.
- Testing of data sources shows that KML has proven to be the standard format for spatial data for geospatial information system software.
- The system has been able to process KML data into an output in the form of an API with the GeoJson format that is in accordance with the existing standard.

- The results of the API with the GeoJson format output system can be projected in many software tools to project maps, such as leaflets, osm, etc.
- The results of system performance testing also show results that are on target, namely the system can handle many number of requests in one time.

In addition, the test results also show that by utilizing the database as a data storage medium and the message queue as a request queue processing regulator makes the system performance faster than the system that directly processes KML files without being stored in the database..

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Thank you for the school of electrical and informatics - Bandung Institute of Technology, especially the digital media engineering and game master's program, which has provided an opportunity for writers to conduct this research.

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